

Discussion Paper: Towards a Sustainable Swiss Research Infrastructure Policy, Funding and Governance Framework¹

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Executive Summary

Research Infrastructures (RIs) are facilities that provide resources and services for research communities. RIs have become increasingly important in recent years for conducting research and foster scientific innovation in many domains complementary to traditional project and career funding instruments.

One of the key problems of the Swiss RI landscape is the lack of a coherent funding, governance, and monitoring model for existing and new research infrastructures. Funding, governance, and monitoring requirements vary greatly based on historical legacies and depending on who has the main responsibility for a RI. This lack of clarity creates confusion and inefficiencies: Considerable efforts must be made by RIs to independently establish a funding and governing model that is accepted, while many of the existing models are constantly put into question. Funding applications as well as monitoring requirements vary substantially also depending on what legal basis an RI is funded. The large variation of models furthermore creates difficulties for funding organizations to steer the process of RI development and funding in a coherent way.

To address these issues the development of a unified legal basis for the funding and governance of RIs is needed. This could be achieved by adding a comprehensive framework article to the Federal Act on the Promotion of Research and Innovation (RIPA), outlining key criteria for the operation of national infrastructures, such as non-profit operation, independent governance, and transparent funding and monitoring mechanisms as well as a coordination mechanism that includes also the national infrastructure roadmap process.

The paper proposes establishing a single national body responsible for RI policymaking and monitoring, ensuring coherence and sustainability. While not responsible for directly funding infrastructures, such a coordinating body should take responsibility that funding models exist in general and for each individual RI. It should not be left to single RIs to try to negotiate independent funding with the different involved actors that do not participate in coordination.

The proposed model emphasizes joint funding by national and higher education institutions and includes standardized governance structures, clear service portfolios, and inclusive access policies. Additionally, it calls for a coordinated monitoring framework to ensure accountability and to measure the outputs and impact of RIs.

Such joint RI policies and funding and governance models will lead to a more coordinated and efficient approach to support the Swiss research community and to enhance Switzerland's position in the global research landscape.

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¹ This paper reflects the personal view of the authors, based on their experience in research infrastructure policy making and management. We would also like to thank various colleagues inside and outside our institutions for their valuable feedback on previous versions.

1 Introduction

In recent decades, research infrastructures (RI) have emerged as crucial pillars of scientific advancement, fostering innovation, collaboration, and knowledge dissemination. Research infrastructures encompass a diverse array of facilities, equipment, technical infrastructures and repositories, and services that are essential for conducting cutting-edge research within or across various disciplines. By providing researchers with access to state-of-the-art technologies, research data and collaborative environments, these infrastructures foster the exploration of complex research questions.

Switzerland has recognized the importance of research infrastructures by establishing a national roadmap process for research infrastructures in 2011. The latest update of the national roadmap was published in 2023 the next planned update for 2027 is ongoing. The Open Research Data Strategy Council (ORD StraCo) was more recently put into place to give strategic input into RI policy making, mostly related to research data infrastructures. ORD StraCo exists alongside swissuniversities Delegation Open Science (DeLOS) that is responsible for Open Science more generally.

With respect to RI policy, funding and governance the following gaps exist, that are also outlined in the comprehensive report established by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)²:

- There is currently a *lack of strategic overview* of national and international research infrastructures (RIs) that are relevant for Swiss researchers currently or in the future, and in relation to the European level. A Swiss national equivalent to the common practice of the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) to conduct a “landscape analysis”, where existing RIs as well as gaps and needs are outlined, does not exist.³ Additionally, there is no comprehensive overview of the funding and the funding sources that go into research infrastructures.
- The current *roadmap process* is rather incomplete, as it does not list existing RIs⁴ along with newly proposed RIs or updates of existing RIs - the focus of the current roadmap is only on the latter. Within the national roadmap process, the application and selection process of projects is not entirely transparent and most likely limited to projects located at higher education institutions which leaves out potential new projects funded through other channels (see chapter 2). For projects from some disciplines, it has therefore been virtually impossible to make it onto the national roadmap because of the aforementioned reasons.
- The *funding, governance, and monitoring* of research infrastructures is far from resolved, especially for new infrastructures. Existing RIs are funded based on historical legacies, with the respective funding, governance and monitoring models that vary substantially depending on the funder.⁵ Only new research infrastructures that are funded by the ETH domain receive secured funding by the State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI). All other RIs have very diverse funding and governance models that are constantly subject to debate and to some extent confusion. While the relevance of RIs is not disputed, there is often a lack of willingness to take responsibility to organise funding due to the lack of standardised funding and governance models and clear roles and responsibilities of the different funding bodies. A lack of clarity exist on the roles and responsibilities exists between national stakeholders, between national and cantonal stakeholders; and furthermore between national and European level stakeholders.

The three elements (i) landscape analysis, (ii) roadmap process, and (iii) funding and governance need to be conceptualized together, while from a governance perspective it may make sense to separate formally the prioritization process from funding and governance (see also position from the Swiss Science Council⁶).

² <https://www.snf.ch/media/en/BliJK4zZIEcq0xIU/SNSF-White-Paper-on-Research-Infrastructures.pdf>

³ This process has now also been decoupled from the roadmap update in ESFRI, and the landscape analysis is conducted before the roadmap update process starts <https://landscape2024.esfri.eu/>.

⁴ The national roadmap process distinguishes between national RIs and the Swiss participation in European RIs. However, given that the funding and governance of national nodes is also not resolved, this paper does not make this distinction, but refers to RIs more generally including such national nodes.

⁵ Some RIs are (co-)funded directly by SERI, some by the Swiss Academies, some by the SNSF. Many RIs are also funded by higher education institutions, mainly for technical facilities (such as labs, computing centers etc.) and some of these facilities do not have a national service portfolio or broad user base.

⁶ Page 28, https://wissenschaftsrat.ch/images/stories/pdf/de/2023_SSC_Stellungnahme_BFI_Botschaft.pdf

Currently the roadmap process takes place in isolation, primarily as a bottom-up process and is neither based on prior and broadly consolidated strategic reflections nor are there consolidated funding and governance models for new RIs that are possible.

This discussion paper focuses on funding and governance, because in some domains work on a landscape analysis related to Data Research Infrastructures are underway (e.g. the ones led by the ORD Strategy Council), and discussions on the future roadmap process are currently also ongoing.

2 The current legal basis for RIs

There are currently no uniform legal requirements for RIs.⁷ The legal basis for funding of RIs is laid out mostly in the Federal Act on the Promotion of Research and Innovation (RIPA):

- Art. 10 funding by the SNSF for “research infrastructures which serve the development of fields of expertise in Switzerland, and which are not within the remit of the higher education research centres or the Confederation”;
- Art. 11 which allows the Swiss Academies to “support international scientific collaboration by funding or running suitable institutions, in particular national coordination platforms” and to support data collections, documentation systems, [...] or similar institutions, which serve as useful infrastructures for the development of fields of expertise in Switzerland and which do not come under the remit of the SNSF or the higher education research centres or do not receive direct support from the Confederation”;
- Art. 15 for “contributions to research facilities of national importance” up to 50% directly from SERI, however with the requirement to also receive “substantial” contributions from cantons and other organizations;
- Art. 28 for “Switzerland’s participation in the development and operation of international research facilities and internationally coordinated research infrastructures”.

In addition, the Federal Act on Funding and Coordination of the Swiss Higher Education Sector (Higher Education Act, HEdA) allows the Confederation through Art. 47 to support shared infrastructure facilities up to 50% of operational costs. To some extent (at least for start-up funding) Art. 59 could also be used since it specifically mentions multi-annual projects for the “creation of national and regional competences centres jointly supported by several higher education institutions”.

This short overview already showcases the potential confusion and lack of clarity regarding what should be funded, given that there is no commonly accepted definition of what constitutes a “research infrastructure”; a “research facility”; or “coordination platforms”.⁸ The funding stream and the legal basis for funding seems much more related to historical legacies than being based on a coherent and agreed strategy.

Furthermore, no uniform model of how to *operate* such facilities exists (see also Annex). Some facilities are legally independent, especially those funded through Art. 15 and also organizations funded by the SNSF (in the case of FORS and DaSCH) or the Academies. The legal form of RIs, varies - some are formed as Associations, some as Foundations and some as institutions or companies. Others are integrated into higher education institutions; this is mainly the case for infrastructure type funding from the SNSF (except for DaSCH and FORS) but also for organizations from other funding streams. The Swiss Academies operate some of the research infrastructures directly within the organization (in the case of SPHN or the “Langzeitunternehmungen” of the SAGW/ASSH).

A more uniform legal basis for the funding and governance of RIs should therefore be developed, including key criteria for the operation of national infrastructures.

At the European Level such a model has been established within the ERIC framework (European Infrastructure Consortium) specifically to overcome the burden of the lack of a standardized funding and governance model for European wide research infrastructures.⁹

⁷ See also the SNSF white paper on that topic.

⁸ See also https://wissenschaftrrat.ch/images/stories/pdf/en/2023_SSC_Report_Lepori_and_Cavallaro.pdf

⁹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32009R0723> and <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/EN/legal-content/summary/european-research-infrastructure-consortium-eric.html>

3 Introducing a new framework article for research infrastructures

In order to advance with creating a joint legal bases for research infrastructures, it is feasible to complement the current legal framework with an overarching new article that also includes RI coordination and outlines key principles of the national roadmap process.

In line with the recommendation from the Swiss Science Council¹⁰ such a framework article could be added to the Federal Act on the Promotion of Research and Innovation (RIPA) in two ways:

- Either regulating key requirements for RIs independent from the funding mechanism that are then relevant for all funding streams into a single framework article for research infrastructures.
- Or integrating similar principles into the different Articles (Art. 10, 11, 15 and 28) and on Article 47 of the HEEdA.

It would also be important to streamline the terminology and definitions used with respect to RIs.

Such an article for national infrastructures should specify (including the nodes of international infrastructures):

- The scope of RIs, e.g. that they should operate in a non-profit way, have a service portfolio and an access policy benefitting the entire Swiss research community.
- Requirements of independence in case of RIs attachment to existing Universities.
- Minimal institutional requirements such as having a governance body with decision making power, including the adoption of budgets that are independent from the host organization, a management and possibly a scientific body.
- Possibly some requirements for distributed infrastructures spread over different institutions or facilities.
- An outline of key funding principles for all research infrastructures.
- Regulation on monitoring (including financial reporting and key performance indicators).
- The requirement to actively participate in coordination e.g. through the formation of RI clusters.

Such an article should further address the issue of RI coordination (e.g. through the ORD Strategy Council, DelOS or a similar body) and outline key principles of the national research infrastructure roadmap process.

4 A joint model for funding and governance of RIs

To ensure coherence and sustainability of national RIs *a single national body should be responsible for research infrastructure policymaking and monitoring*. This could be achieved:

- by the establishment of a new research infrastructure policymaking body. Such a body would need to have the necessary expertise from different disciplines to take into account discipline-specific requirements. Many countries have delegated this task to their research councils; however, in Switzerland there might be limitations to such a model, because other actors than the Swiss National Science Foundation are involved in policymaking and funding, such as the Academies or SERI. Currently there is a lack of clarity at many levels, from responsibilities within the roadmap process to funding and governance of RIs; or
- by an extension of the role of the current ORD Strategy Council beyond ORD related topics. Many of the current infrastructures collect data either at the national level or in a European framework that do not seem to be within the current responsibility of the ORD Strategy Council. This also requires a clarification of the division of tasks between the ORD Strategy Council and DelOs.

Such a coordinating body should also *take responsibility that funding models exist* in general and for each individual RI and give a clear pathway how an RI can be funded. It should not be left to a single RI to try independently negotiate funding with the different potential actors that do not coordinate among themselves.

RIs have some specific features which require some specific models of funding, governance, and monitoring outside of the known project funding mechanisms. The main mission of RIs is to provide services for parts or an entire discipline as a whole, or even several disciplines, on a national scale, rather than to conduct primary

¹⁰ Page 28 https://wissenschaftsrat.ch/images/stories/pdf/de/2023_SSC_Stellungnahme_BFI_Botschaft.pdf

research. It is important to recognize that RIs are not a tool to conduct research for a single researcher or a group of researchers or a single institution, since they provide services for parts of an entire discipline as a whole and often long term, beyond the scope of a single research project.

Considering this, we propose the following *general mechanisms for funding*:

- Funding of *research infrastructures should in all cases be jointly secured by those who fund research*, which is the national level, e.g. through the National Science Foundation, as well as higher education institutions.
- The national key actors as well as higher education institutions (SERI, SNF, swissuniversities, academies) should have a clear joint policy and agreement regarding RI standards of funding, governance and monitoring, since these are all national funds channelled through different sources.
- A *general funding model relevant for all infrastructures should be developed*, with national funds as a basis, which are complemented by additional funds from higher education institutions. A typical model of a RI would include national funds (the sums of which may vary), complemented by contributions from a host university or institution as well as other institutions. This requires that all national as well as cantonal higher education organizations should agree on a joint model of how to fund national infrastructures.

With respect to *governance*, we propose the following general principles:

- Given that research infrastructures provide a national service, they require a *high level of independence* from their host institution. This can be marked by a legal independence (as is the case for SIB, FORS, and DaSCH), or it can be regulated with a certain degree of autonomy within an institution, if the service is integrated within a higher education institution.
- Research infrastructures typically have one or multiple host institution. Those *host institutions may have specific rights and duties*.
- Research infrastructures shall have a clear *service portfolio as well as access policies regarding their data, services, and resources*. Given the national mission of RIs, services and access should, in principle, be beneficial to all researchers from higher education institutions in Switzerland from a certain discipline.
- Research infrastructures should have an *independent level of governance*, which includes at least one governing board that has clear roles and responsibilities.
- Since national funds are involved, this also means that *representatives from national funding bodies (SNF, academies, SERI) should be involved in the appropriate governance structure(s) of RIs*.
- Research infrastructures should *ensure that the respective research community is included in the governance and especially the scientific development of an RI*. If not in the main governing body, this can be through a scientific advisory body. This is especially important for RIs that are single sited and/or attached to a single institution. If they have national recognition, they should also ensure inclusion of the entire Swiss research community in the respective discipline.

Monitoring of research infrastructures should be based on a coherent monitoring framework which applies to all RIs:

- RIs should be monitored in regular intervals. They may provide qualitative and key performance indicators (KPIs) that are agreed on by the governing bodies. One approach could be to select KPIs from the list established by ESFRI,¹¹ possibly using a similar approach, since some of the Swiss nodes of ESFRI RIs have to provide this information anyway.
- Additionally, a new requirement from ESFRI is that RIs may showcase their impact, scientific and other types of impact in a comprehensive way.¹² This might become increasingly important in Switzerland as well.

Such a monitoring framework and the expectations of RIs should be agreed upon in advance given that the collection of the measures is time consuming.

¹¹ https://www.esfri.eu/sites/default/files/ESFRI_WG_Monitoring_Report.pdf

¹² See the respective policy document established by ESFRI <https://www.esfri.eu/esfri-policy-brief-impact>

5 Benefits of such a legal, funding and governance framework

There are many benefits from such a framework article.

Overall:

- Increased clarity and coherence on RI policy, funding and governance should also facilitate steering the process of RI prioritisation in the national strategic interest.
- Instead of having (at least) four different funding modes each with its own roles (see chapter 2), a single framework would result in increased transparency and efficiency.

For SERI:

- Given that national RIs and the Swiss nodes of international RIs are also becoming of greater strategic importance, clarity on the funding and governance of RIs is key to further developing the competitiveness of the Swiss research sector.

Higher education institutions:

- Clarity on how to fund and operate different research infrastructures.
- To have incentives for hosting a national research infrastructure and to compete for hosting. Ideally, as a RI gains visibility and expertise, the funding will not rely solely on a single higher education institution.

For research infrastructures:

- For existing infrastructures national in scope, to have the stability and assurance of an accepted funding and governance model and to be relieved of the responsibility to independently find funding solutions.
- To gain visibility and security on requirements for monitoring of performance and impact.

Such a joint model also has some disadvantages. Developing a standardized funding and governance model will no doubt limit the diversity of models available, even if many specificities are considered. It will also require both funders and RIs to adapt their practices in funding structures and distribution and steering and managing RIs.

Shifting funding structures and models may raise fears and concerns among stakeholders, with the risk of preventing possibilities and further future discussions on joint models for RI policy, governance and funding. Therefore, it is important to consider the different concerns and to ensure to key stakeholders that such a reform will serve to streamline and strengthen the entire RI landscape in Switzerland, ensuring sustainability and increasing value.

6 The way forward

Working on a new framework article is the way forward to approach research infrastructure funding and governance in a comprehensive way. This offers a way out of the current situation where many key actors as well as the different research infrastructures are highly unsatisfied.

Given that research infrastructures are nowadays core facilities for scientific innovation, more strategy, clarity and coherence on infrastructure policy and prioritization would strengthen the Swiss research sector as a whole also in the European and Global Science competition.

The lead on developing such a new legal basis for research infrastructures needs to be with SERI as part of the federal government tasked with research and innovation policy. However, the concrete proposal to move forward in this direction could either come by SERI themselves, by any national actor such as swissuniversities or from the national parliament.

7 Annex: Example of existing research infrastructures in Switzerland

This Annex provides **selected examples of research infrastructures in Switzerland but not an overview**. Its mainly based on publicly available information, not all institutions were asked to review the information themselves. The objective is to demonstrate the points outlined in the paper, that the structure, governance and funding sources vary greatly across infrastructures.

Research Infrastructure	Communities Served	Services Provided	Governance Bodies	Host Institution	Funding Source & Legal Basis	Funding Cycle	Additional Information
Swiss National Data and Service Center for the Humanities (DaSCH) [Legal status]: Association	Humanities researchers in Swiss HEIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research data management support services • Research data curation and preservation (DSP & SWISSUbase platforms) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assembly of Delegates • Board of the Association • Scientific Advisory Board • Executive Board 	University of Basel	Source: Swiss National Science Foundation Legal Basis: Article 10 RIPA	2025-2028	In 2017, DaSCH was established as a national facility operated by SAGW with a mandate set out in the ERI Dispatch 2017–2020. Since 2021, DaSCH has operated as a national research data infrastructure primarily funded by SNSF. DaSCH is also the national node of DARIAH ERIC.
Diplomatic Documents of Switzerland (DODIS) [Legal status]: No legal status, Institute of SAGW	Humanities researchers and stakeholders in Switzerland (and abroad), mainly from history	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online Database on Diplomatic Documents • DODIS Print Edition and Bibliography • Conducts fundamental research on Swiss contemporary history 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific Council (Kommission) 	Institute of the Swiss Academy of Humanities and Social Sciences in Bern	Source: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Swiss Academy of Humanities and Social Sciences • Academic grants Legal Basis: Article 11 RIPA	2025-2028	Under the patronage of the Swiss Historical Society, supported by the Swiss Federal Archives and the Federal Dept. of Foreign Affairs.
Swiss Centre of Expertise in the Social Sciences (FORS) [Legal status]: Foundation	Social sciences researchers in Swiss HEIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data collection and analysis • Research data management & support services • Research data curation and preservation (SWISSUbase platform) • Coordination of national and international projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FORS Foundation Board • FORS Scientific Advisory Board • FORS Executive Board 	University of Lausanne	Source: Swiss National Science Foundation Legal Basis: Art. 10 RIPA	2025-2028	FORS is also the national node of CESSDA ERIC and ESS ERIC
Language Repository of Switzerland (LaRS)	Linguistics researchers in Swiss HEIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research data management & support services 	SWISSUbase Oversight Board	University of Zurich	Source: University of Zurich	Until 2026	LaRS, through the University of Zurich, is a

<p>[Legal status]: Simple Society – partner of the SWISSUbase Consortium</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research data curation and preservation (SWISSUbase platform) 			<p>Legal Basis: -</p>		<p>member of the SWISSUbase Consortium (consisting of FORS and the Universities of Lausanne, Zurich and Neuchâtel).</p>
<p>Swiss Art Research Infrastructure (SARI)</p> <p>[Legal status]: Not specified</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific communities of the UZH, Switzerland, and abroad, covering small-scale to large-scale projects at universities and in the GLAM (Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums) sector. • External, non-academic users 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology Platform • Access to research data and visual research resources • Semantic network based on standards • Research environment for teaching and research in the Humanities • 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Executive Board • Research Affiliates • Advisory Board 	<p>Hosted by University of Zurich</p> <p>Partnership with ETH Zurich and the Swiss Institute for Art Research, Zurich</p>	<p>Source: Fee structure is dependent on user categories:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Internal users: mandates by UZH clients (incl. SARI Research) 2. External academic users: mandates by academic clients outside UZH 3. Non-academic users: external mandates by non-academic clients <p>Legal Basis: -</p>	<p>Members and clients pay fees.</p>	
<p>Swiss Data Science Centre (SDSC)</p> <p>[Legal status]: Not specified</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ETH Domain • Swiss academic community • Public institutions & NGOs • Private sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data science support & services in gathering, analyzing and leveraging data across disciplines. • AI and data science strategy for organisations • Coaching and consulting: projects, strategies, recruitment • Training 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Management team 	<p>Hosted by EPFL.</p> <p>Offices in Zurich & Villigen.</p> <p>Partnership with ETH Zurich and PSI (research institute for natural & engineering sciences).</p>	<p>Source: ETH Domain</p> <p>Legal Basis: -</p>		<p>In 2017, a national Data Science initiative from the ETH Board resulted in the creation of a unique strategic focus area: the Swiss Data Science Center (SDSC), bringing together the ETH Zürich, the EPFL, and the PSI.</p>
<p>Swiss Bioinformatics Institute (SIB)</p> <p>[Legal status]: Independent scientific foundation</p>	<p>Biomedical and Biological science researchers and clinicians in Switzerland:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Academic & public-private consortia - Hospitals & clinics - Private sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biostatistics and bioinformatics analysis • Research data management & support services • Data curation and preservation • Sensitive data sharing • Software development • Training 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foundation Council • Board of Directors • Scientific Advisory Board • Council of Group Leaders • SIB Hub 	<p>Offices at the University of Geneva, Lausanne, and Zurich (from 2025 onward).</p>	<p>Source (2023 budget):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SERI base subsidy (36%) • Competitive grants (19%) • Collaborations & Services (13%) • Other income (6%) • BioMedIT / SPHN subsidies (25%) <p>Legal Basis: -</p>	<p>2025-2028</p>	<p>SIB was founded in 1998 in Geneva and now consists of 28 institutional partners across Switzerland.</p>

<p>Swiss Personalized Health Network (SPHN)</p> <p>[Legal status]: No legal status; special mandate in the ERI-Dispatches 2017-2028</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (University) Hospitals • Health data providers • Higher education institutions • Researchers in health and medicine 	<p>Development, implementation and validation of coordinated data infrastructures to make health-relevant data interoperable and shareable for research in Switzerland.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SPHN National Steering Board • BioMedIT Board • 	<p>Swiss Academy of Medical Sciences (SAMS) & SIB</p>	<p>Source:</p> <p>State Secretary for Education, Research, and Innovation (SERI) and matching funds of beneficiaries.</p> <p>Legal Basis:</p> <p>ERI-Dispatches 2017-2028</p>	<p>2017-2024: SPHN initiative</p> <p>2025-2028: SPHN Data Coordination Center</p>	
<p>Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cluster (SSHOC-CH)</p> <p>[Legal status]: Association</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National infrastructures in SSH domain • National nodes of international infrastructures in SSH domain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exchange and cooperation of RI to support research projects and researchers • Identify and foster synergies • Connection with SSHOC at the European level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Executive Board 	<p>N/A</p>	<p>Source:</p> <p>Annual membership fee: 40 CHF</p> <p>Legal Basis:</p> <p>-</p>	<p>Members pay annual fees</p>	

Sources:

DaSCH

Governance: <https://www.dasch.swiss/governance>

Funding: <https://www.dasch.swiss/about-us>

DODIS

Funding and Governance: <https://www.dodis.ch/en>

FORS

Governance: <https://forscenter.ch/about-fors/governance/>

LaRS

Governance: <https://info.swissubase.ch/resources/?sr=2317>

SARI

About: <https://www.sari.uzh.ch/en.html>

Governance: <https://www.sari.uzh.ch/en/organisation.html>

Funding / Fees: <https://www.sari.uzh.ch/en/services/fees.html>

SDSC

About: <https://www.datascience.ch/innovation>

Governance: <https://www.datascience.ch/team>

SIB

Governance: <https://www.sib.swiss/about/governance-and-organization>

Funding: <https://www.sib.swiss/about/funding-sources>

Services: <https://slsp.ch/en/basic-services/>

SPHN

Governance: <https://sphn.ch/organization/governance/>

Funding: <https://sphn.ch/services/funding/>

SSHOC-CH

Governance: <https://sshoc.ch/association>